

E-Marketing: Opportunities and Issues

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Abstract

E-marketing is growing at a dramatic pace and is significantly impacting customer and business market behaviors. As a result, most firms have started developing e-marketing strategies for the web. However, the evolution and strategic direction of e-marketing strategies in international environments has not been discussed and is the focus of this paper. Design/methodology/approach – In the paper, the authors examine two issues based on extant literature and our previous research in this area. The authors discuss e-marketing in an international context and develop a framework that will allow researchers and managers to understand the impact of country-level effects on e-marketing strategies. The paper proposes that the evolution of e-marketing strategies is based on the country’s infrastructure and marketing institutional development. Findings – It is found that international e-marketing strategies are fundamentally changing, and will continue to change, marketing thought and practiced in international markets. The paper suggests that the e-markets of tomorrow may have little resemblance to the markets of today. The proposed strategies are – brick and click strategies, digitization, disintermediation, buying groups and alternative infrastructure, firm driven e-marketing strategies, and corporate exchanges. Originality/value – The paper is the first attempt to examine the relationship between a country’s infrastructure, marketing institutions and the appropriate e-marketing strategies.

Keywords: E-marketing, E-commerce, future of marketing, opportunities for marketers

Introduction

Internet “refers to the physical network that links computers across the globe. It consists of the infrastructure of network servers and wide area communication links between them that are used to hold and transport the vast amount of information on the internet”. Online marketing is no longer an option; it is a necessity. Still, that’s not all bad news. Planning your Internet marketing strategy does not have to be a difficult task, particularly if the competition doesn’t fully understand that the rules of Internet marketing are not the rules of traditional marketing. The Internet is a dynamic system, with both companies and consumers having to adapt to the rapid pace at which it moves. For companies, this means that competition has become global. Target demographics are no longer geographically limited,

expanding across countries and continents. These expansions, though, mean that companies have to adapt different types of strategies from what they are used to with online marketing. E-Marketing or electronic marketing refers to the application of marketing principles and techniques via electronic media and more specifically the Internet. The terms e-Marketing, Internet marketing and online marketing, are frequently interchanged, and can often be considered synonymous. E-Marketing is the process of marketing a brand using the Internet. E-marketing means using digital technologies to help sell your goods or services. E-Marketing is the fusion of IT with traditional marketing.

E-Marketing

E-marketing is growing at a dramatic pace and is significantly impacting customer and business market behaviors. As a result, most firms started developing e-marketing strategies. E-marketing strategies entail utilizing existing and emerging communication and data networks to impart personalized and uninterrupted communication between the firm and its customers and to provide value above traditional networks. Marketing also became more organization initiated as products were first manufactured and then marketed. E-marketing creates a fundamental shift in business and consumer behaviors similar to that associated with the introduction of smart phones that reduced the need for channel immediacy. E-marketing uses the Internet as a platform that allows firms to adapt to the needs of customers, reduces transaction costs, and allows customers to move from time and location-based behaviors toward non-temporal and non-locational behaviors. E-marketing is similar to agricultural-age marketing, with direct recurring relationships between consumer and producer but with lower costs. The main advantages of e-marketing are cost reduction and enhancing reach. The cost of an e-marketing platform is typically lower than other marketing platforms such as face-to-face salespeople or middlemen/ distributors. E-marketing platforms increase reach and reduce costs by providing three areas of advantage for customers. First, the marketing firm can provide unlimited information to customers without human intervention. Second, the e-marketing firm can create interactions by customizing information for individual customers that allow customers to design products and services that meet their specific requirements. Finally, e-marketing platforms can allow transactions between customers and firms that would typically require human contact as in the case of successful firms such as flipcart.com, amazon.com and snapdeal.com.

Electronic Environment for Marketing Purpose

New on-line marketing tools comprise: various forms of e-mail (from simple text messages to advanced HTML ones, employing Flash technology), tools based on e-mail: 1. electronic newsletters (text and HTML ones), 2. Discussion lists, 3. Newsgroups, 4. auto responders, Web pages (the most popular on-line advertising medium) and numerous forms of Internet advertising used there, e.g. banners (stationary, animated or interactive e.g. tele banner), pop-up ads, interstitials, poltergeist, media break, Active Pilot, Charlie Behind (pop-out), Micro Ads (sponsored links). According to a study of Double-click conducted in December 2001, one-half of surveyed marketers employs on-line marketing techniques, In fact with the development of the Internet, tool kit available to marketers has been significantly enriched. But if someone expected that because of their interactive nature, new marketing tools would be commonly employed by companies for building close relationships with customers and “one-sided bombardment, common in a real world, will be widely replaced on-line by dialogue must be disappointed. If fact as a result of the Internet usage for marketing purpose, this “one side bombardment” became far more troublesome for consumers and it is expected that situation will be getting worse in the next few years.

The Future of Marketing

The future is important, yet it is notoriously difficult to predict, and the difficulty increases as the time horizon extends. But the globalization of the Markets; the Increased importance of Information Globalization and technological advances have greatly advanced the business opportunities for Marketing. The increased number of people traveling worldwide in addition to international migration has meant that marketing innovations have to meet the needs of the clients and have to be convenient for everyone. The marketing function of the future will continue to be polarized. Aker highlighted that in a growing number of businesses, marketing would have more of a strategic role. That means the marketing group must have the skills and talent to think strategically and the credibility to influence the process to think regarding building branded assets rather than immediate sales. They need to work sales, product, and finance colleagues to support process improvements and to implement the necessary e-marketing measures. Marketing is changing, and we should expect it to change. Accounting has been with us since the late 1400's and is likely to be with us for some time yet. This is not to say that it has evolved and changed during that time, but the essential feature-to provide a fair and accurate statement of the financial health of a firm-has remained unaltered. With Marketing, we do expect it to evolve from door-to-door guerrilla marketing to more diversified e-marketing, smart phones have become a necessity, technology has increased and marketer needs to find a way for the future and see to it that e-marketing becomes their primary target.

E-Marketing: Opportunities for the Marketers

The growth of the Internet had increased competition tremendously and opened up the doors to international business. Companies have developed a web presence to keep themselves ahead or in line with their competitors internationally. In addition to gaining a competitive advantage, there are some additional reasons why a company's web presence is becoming an increasingly important tool to reach global markets. Internet Population - Internet access is increasing in regions throughout the world. According to the Computer Industry Almanac, 533 million people have access to the Internet, which represents approximately 8 percent of the world's population. Aberdeen Group predicts that by the end of 2005, 17 percent of the worldwide population will have Internet access Demand for Products and Services - Regions throughout the world realize the enormous information resource the Web is and are interested in content, and products and services that their regions do not provide. Online Payment - A barrier that blocked E-commerce growth throughout the world, particularly in Europe, was different currencies. However, adoption of the Euro is completed, phasing out local currencies and blurring borders between countries in the European Union. By enabling better price comparisons, increasing competition and improving deals for online buyers, the Euro is making it easier to conduct business in the European online market and providing better entry by non-European companies. Marketing and Advertising - Online marketing is a popular method to gain international audiences. For example, Email has become one of the most successful channels for marketers in Europe, which means that companies interested in selling to the European online market should take advantage of this popular medium. Increased Sales and Reduced Costs - A web site provides an avenue through which to gain access to a large audience without spending a lot of money. For example, it cuts down on paper costs associated with direct marketing and magazine or newspaper advertising.

Conclusion

Technology is affecting the form, flow, speed, delivery channels and credibility of information in everything we do. Consumers are now able to make better-informed judgments than ever before

about everything and purchases and are now the “go to” authorities for each other about the value and reliability of products. Online marketing strategy is something that any company or business is capable of organizing and administering on their own. Despite globalization speed and the extent of information that can be gained from E-marketing will surely help the business to develop when implemented properly.

On the other hand, the technology-driven approach of E-marketing leaves certain businesses vulnerable and overly dependent upon technology. With planning and careful execution, any business can reap the benefits of a strategic online marketing plan. Marketing is the gateway to a company that an individual steps through, but it remains only the beginning. A solid online marketing strategy should be backed by strong work ethic, morals, and a desire to please customers. In the end, we concluded that “e-marketing is the future of the marketing field.” With common objectives, the right method, any one that does incorporate.

E-marketing will be left with the small percentage of people to market to, in the sense that the majority have moved on with technology and are using gadgets and smart phones. However, the view presented here is that the future belongs to e-marketing in the marketing field, but not limited to it.

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